

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A579

20 September 1997

ACSOE

Frontal crossing flight

A579, 20th September, 1997
 ACSOE
 North Atlantic near the Azores

Start time	End time	Event	Height(s)	Hdg	Comments
110242					Take off St Maria
111449	112746	R1	FL80	080°	
113416	120941	P1	50' FL170	075°	
120941	121709	R2	FL170	355°	
121709	124648	P2	FL170 50'	355°	Bottles filled @ FL130 FL70,3000',500'.
124648	133550	P3	50' FL240		Bottles filled @ 100' 3000'FL70,FL100,FL150, FL240
133550	134009	R3	FL240	280°	
134009	142645	P4	FL240 50'	295°	Bottles filled @ FL214 FL200,FL150,FL110,FL50 500'
142645	151323	P5	50' FL260	275°	Bottles filled @ 100', FL50,FL110,FL150,FL200
151323	151822	R4	FL260	165°	
151822	160509	P6	FL260 50'	170°	Bottles filled @ FL200 FL150,FL130,FL110,FL50 500'
160509	165236	P7	50' FL260	160°	Bottles filled @ 100' FL50,FL110,FL150,FL200
165236	165639	R5	FL260	160°	
165639	170520	P8	FL260 FL100	165°	
170520	1715	R6	FL100	165°	
175003					Land Santa Maria

A579 ACSOE SCIENCE

September 20, 1997

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

To observe the atmospheric chemical composition in Atlantic air North of the Azores. The data will be added to a systematically collected airmass data base and will be used to determine the oxidising capacity and the budget of tropospheric oxidants in marine air at mid latitudes in the northern hemisphere.

LOCATION:

Northeast Atlantic Ocean, North of the Azores.

WEATHER:

Cloud Free

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Santa Maria.
 - [1.1] Hold climb at 3000 ft for wet chemistry check.
- [2] Standard climb to FL080.
 - [2.1] Run for NO_x Calibration (15 min).
- [3] Standard descent to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude).
- [4] Profile from 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) to maximum altitude — 500ft/min to top of boundary layer then 1000ft/min. Interrupt profile at FL100 for zeroes.
- [5] Stepped Sawtooth from maximum altitude to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) — 1000ft/min to top of boundary layer then 500ft/min. Carry out zeroes and fill bottles as requested.
 - [5.1] Repeat as time allows.
- [6] Profile descent from maximum altitude to FL080.
 - [6.1] Run for NO_x Calibration (12 min) — Science speed & Constant altitude
 - [6.2] Run for NO_x Artifacts (15 min) — Constant altitude
 - [6.3] Run for Noxy shut down (10 min) — Pilot/Nav discretion
- [7] Return to Santa Maria, visual examination of Santa Mairia's coastal micro-meteorology.
- [8] Land.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure and temperature to be kept constant on level runs. The NO_x should ideally be zeroed every 15 minutes. During profiles this should be done at the start of grab sample runs. Other instrument operators should perform zeros at this time if required.

TIME:

6 Hours and 30 Minutes

AZORES/C-130

Science Brief for Flight of 20/9/97

Take off time 11:00Z.

Scientific Rationale

There is some indication from the trajectories that air north west of Santa Maria at around 20,000 ft may have been near the surface five days ago on the west of the US, lifted up to 20,000 ft and transported rapidly over Canada and out over the Atlantic. This type of flow seemed quite widespread based on the forecasts a couple of days ago. However the most recent forecasts suggest a more confused pattern. This is largely due to a frontal system moving from the west. The comparison flight with the P3 on Wednesday (17/9/97) was carried out in the clear air just in front (to the east) of this cold front. The P3 flew through the front on route to the rendezvous point and again on its return to St. Johns. The first cut was at FL 200 and within cloud the concentrations of NO_y , HNO_3 , and O_3 increased. The second cut was at FL 180 and again NO_y and O_3 increased.

The plan is to fly in (almost) a triangular type pattern from 38N22W to 44N24W to 44N30W to 38W24W. The first leg will be east of the front and approximately perpendicular to the flow. The second leg will be east to west, across and perpendicular to the front. The third leg will be homeward to Santa Maria. Each leg will be made of deep stepped profiles up to high altitudes hoping to intersect air that has been transported over Canada. We will want to fly in cloud free air, but a fair amount of cloud is expected.

Suggested step levels on descent: FL250 (or max altitude), FL200, FL150, FL100, FL050, 500ft

Suggested step levels on ascent: 100ft, FL050, FL100, FL150, FL200, FL250 (or max altitude)

These may change, depending on observations.

Visual examination of Santa Maria's coastal micro-meteorology.

Landing at Santa Maria 17:30Z.

Debrief

The original aim of the experiment, based on earlier trajectory calculations, had been to investigate high level transport of air from the US. However, the latest available trajectories, for flight planning, had not indicated such an outflow. It was therefore decided to use the meteorological situation to carry out a frontal crossing sortie. Profiles were carried out to the east of the cold front, through the cold front and to the west of the front before returning to Santa Maria. The surface cold front was marked by a band of mainly convective cloud: no precipitation was noted. The front was clearly not very active and the frontal zone ill-defined. However, interesting layers were observed with distinct changes in chemical and physical parameters. Although, the front was not very marked detailed analysis of the data may prove interesting.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *Lucas*

Project: *ACSE ~~MSA~~*
 Flight No: *A579*

Date: *21 9 1977*
 Page 1 of 10

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				Longitude	
11:05:00		8000 feet	68	36.95 -24.75	2000 feet run slight inversion on top of 900 mb (at 1800 feet)
11:12:47		060		37.00 -24.61	inversion. small amounts of broken stratus / cu beneath.
11:40:05					over narrow stratus sheet back to broken cu (3/8) by 11/4 & 9
11:44:19	Run 1	0800	65	37.04 -24.46	Noisy cal broken stratus both above and below. Some larger cu in distance / mixed stratus / cu / stratus below 4/8. Thicker stratus / stratus above.
11:58					stratus sheet below occasionally broken, thinner broken stratus above
12:24:46	end Run 1/1				
"	start P1				No structure in CO, NOx, NOy, temp decreases readily.
		1800			broken cu (small) at this level
11:34	P2			37.56 -23.10	ascent from 80 feet IAT=22 a Dew=21 173/10
11:35		800 feet		37.62 -23.00	low cloud on 500 feet thick height 800 feet / run 2 thickness varying. all the way

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: RICHEN

Project: ACSOE ~~1000~~

Date: 20/09/97

Flight No: A579

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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1138	P2	2700 Pres Rad FL	68	37.68 -22.90	Above cloud at 2700 feet chem parameters identical on way back up.
1140					cloud free area
114330	P2	5300 Pres Rad FL	70	37.81 -22.50	above shubs on deck / cu (small) 7/8 No cloud above
1146	P2	6500 Pres Rad FL	65	37.83 -22.43	Temperature inversion increased ozone / drier air
11				37.95 -22.11	very shallow layer with O ₃ decrease per SO - 25, No 400ft, CNC, INC.
115102	Interrupt P2	090 Pres Rad FL	70	38.00 -22.00	Interrupt, zeros for all instruments (except CH ₂ O)
115422	Recomm P2	9000 Pres Rad FL	345		Max alt of profile FL170 due to ATC (vertical)
115735					Some shubs now above 7/8
12				38.70 -22.19	level with cloud altostratus
120630		15400 Pres Rad FL			Air drying out
120941	R2	170 Pres Rad FL		39.22 -22.30	zeros and battle run. low zero for peroxide

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: R. CHOR

Project: ACSSE
Flight No: A579

Date: 20/09/97
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121709	P2	170 Pres Rad FL	345	39.58 -22.41	1000 feet/min
122107	Interrupt P2	130 Pres Rad FL		7	
122	reconnect P2				
122952		370 Pres Rad FL	342	40.36 -22.65	CO ₂ O ₃ drop - most marked in O ₃ down to 21 ppb from 60 ppb. (Min 18 ppb O ₃) are increasing again. essentially the low O ₃ was very distinct and found at different altitudes in different profiles - FL 10 in P2 FL 150 in P1 Changes in O ₃ also correspond with O ₂ changes - very well anticorrelated
12378	Interrupt 2000 feet			40.80 -22.81	
1239	P2 reconnect			40.90 -22.84	
1244	Interrupt 500	500 Pres Rad FL		41.17 -22.94	
124648	P3 (end P2)			4.29 -22.96	TAS 164, TAT, 20.6, Dew 18.4, Wind 1.63/8
125204	Interrupt 2000			4.57 -23.08	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *RICHARD*

Project: *ACRSE*
Flight No: *AS701*

Date: *20/09/97*
Page *4* of *10*

*tips of
fuel tank
to FL 20*

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude ----- Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
<i>125420</i>	<i>interrupt restart P3</i>	<i>8500 feet Pres Rad FL</i>	<i>340</i>	<i>41.70 -23.12</i>	<i>Stratus on below stratus, altostratus above</i>
<i>125843</i>	<i>interrupt P3</i>	<i>70 Pres Rad FL</i>		<i>42.01 23.22</i>	<i>0345, 0070 zero for check instruments</i>
<i>130233</i>	<i>restart P3</i>	<i>70 Pres Rad FL</i>		<i>42.18 -23.28</i>	<i>Frontal cloud noted to West. request change in heading to stay to the east of the front</i>
<i>130522</i>	<i>interrupt</i>	<i>100 Pres Rad FL</i>			<i>little fl. High cloud (cirrus) noted to the east. Bank of cloud including embedded cumulus</i>
<i>1307</i>	<i>restart P3</i>	<i>100 Pres Rad FL</i>	<i>032</i>	<i>42.50 -23.27</i>	<i>to the West. Altocum above Stratus below change in OW 1305</i>
<i>1311</i>		<i>Pres Rad FL</i>			<i>change in OW (back up) "warm side"</i>
<i>131324</i>	<i>interrupt</i>	<i>150 Pres Rad FL</i>		<i>42.71 -22.93</i>	<i>little</i>
<i>131809</i>	<i>restart P3</i>	<i>Pres Rad FL</i>			
<i>132946</i>	<i>interrupt</i>	<i>220 Pres Rad FL</i>		<i>43.84 -22.12</i>	<i>turn + Calcs</i>
<i>133228</i>	<i>restart</i>	<i>220 Pres Rad FL</i>	<i>212</i>		
<i>133550</i>		<i>240 Pres Rad FL</i>		<i>43.57 -22.21</i>	<i>typical shows much structure</i>

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *W. L. H. C. S.*

Project: *ACSIA*
 Flight No: *A579*

Date: *20/09/97*
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
<i>134009</i>	<i>P4</i>				
<i>134406</i>	<i>interrupt</i> <i>P4</i>	<i>244</i>		<i>43.35</i> <i>22.84</i>	<i>bottle of FL240 lost refilled FL24</i> <i>albac above</i>
<i>1345</i>	<i>recommence</i>			<i>43.35</i> <i>-22.97</i>	
<i>134777</i>	<i>interrupt</i> <i>200</i>	<i>200</i>			<i>circus + altostratus above, stratocum below</i> <i>bottles</i>
<i>135044</i>	<i>restart</i>	<i>120</i>		<i>43.39</i> <i>-23.40</i>	
<i>13523</i>	<i>interrupt</i>	<i>150</i>		<i>43.50</i> <i>-23.88</i>	<i>bottles</i>
<i>135928</i>	<i>restart</i> <i>P4</i>	<i>150</i>		<i>43.56</i> <i>-24.13</i>	<i>no cloud above</i> <i>broken stratocum below base of cloud both</i> <i>stratiform + cumuloform clouds seen - surface</i> <i>front?</i>
<i>140230</i>		<i>115</i>		<i>43.61</i> <i>-24.36</i>	<i>coming under stratiform cloud</i>
<i>140359</i>	<i>interrupt</i>	<i>110</i>		<i>43.63</i> <i>-24.49</i>	<i>under stratiform cloud</i>
<i>140743</i>	<i>P4</i>			<i>43.69</i> <i>-24.76</i>	<i>restart</i>

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist:

Project: ACsøE
Flight No: A579

Date: 20/09/97
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude ----- Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14251 14251 141351	Intercept	5000	290	43.84 -25.44	entering tops of cumulus clouds / stratocumulus
14253	revert P4				bit of cirrus piling down 500 feet/min in cloud.
		3500			clear of cloud stratocum below stratiform cloud above.
1421					Back into cloud - follow stratiform
142210					Back out of cloud Back into 1423 - stratiform.
142349		800			in thin stratiform (fog)
142540	revert P4			44.00 -25.99	
14		5000			
142701	low level			44.01 -26.07	TAT 19.4, DEW 18.2, wind 224/3 - mostly clear band of stratocum ahead.
142948					going through top of cloud - marked change
		50			

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *RICHARD*

Project: *ACSOE*
 Flight No: *A579*

Date: *20/9/97*
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude ----- Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
143725		500 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>			<i>Q</i>
144336		110 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>		<i>44.08 -27.40</i>	<i>1441 onwards marked change in NO_x, NO_y here layer whole to starboard - humidity dec. O₃ inc. CO - no really marked change changes increases but not so markedly stops</i>
144622	<i>cont p5</i>				
145003	<i>Interrupt</i>	150 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	267	<i>44.09 -27.80</i>	
145406	<i>restart</i>	150 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>		<i>44.09</i>	<i>FL100 → FL150 high O₃ & NO_y Hazy below some cirrus to port some cumulus clouds in distance to starboard</i>
150020	<i>interrupt</i>	200 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	258	<i>44.08 -28.54</i>	
150325	<i>restart</i>	200 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	288	<i>44.05 -28.81</i>	<i>High NO_x, NO_y, O₃, FL170 → FL200</i>
15		280 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>		<i>44.02 -29.42</i>	<i>wind 235/27</i>
151323	<i>Rk end p5</i>	260 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	257	<i>44.02 -29.60</i>	<i>-marked cloudy to starboard</i>
151822	<i>p6 end 24</i>	260 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	153	<i>43.89 -29.93</i>	
152454	<i>interrupt p6</i>	200 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>		<i>43.54 -29.44</i>	<i>batteries</i>

As cloud above or below

23

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: RICHOL

Project: ACSOE
Flight No: A579

Date: 20/09/97
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
152820	P6 restart	200 Pres Rad FL			
153404	interrupt	150 Pres Rad FL		43.9 -28.94	stratocumulus in O ₃ + NO _y not so clear on this profile
153722	restart P6	13 Pres Rad FL		42.88 -28.77	
153935	interrupt	130 Pres Rad FL	154	42.64 -28.53	
154313	restart P6			42.59 -28.47	
154511	interrupt	110 Pres Rad FL		42.49 -28.38	(broken) altostratus above / some cirrus 4/8 (OKS) showing below but some small cu to port side
154908	restart	110 Pres Rad FL	184	42.30 -28.14	cirrus above / stratiform clouds above 4/8 few small cu below (less than 1 over)
155220		7800 Pres Rad FL		42.15 -28.85	hazy layer temp inversion (7700 feet 750 mb) - no cloud at this level but almost saturated on temp
155458	interrupt	50 Pres Rad FL		42.02 -27.93	
155655	restart P6			41.94 -27.86	very hazy / misty

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *Richard*

Project: AC 80E
Flight No: A579

Date: ²⁰ 10/19/97
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
16029		850 ^{Pres} ^{Rad} ^{FL}			bottom run frontal cloud to aft / front of plane
160349				41.63 -27.60	some small c above 3/8
160412	restart P6		153	41.61 -27.59	" (high cloud above that?)
160509	end P6 start P7	50 ^{Pres} ^{Rad} ^{FL}			
160524	restart P7	100 ^{Pres} ^{Rad} ^{FL}	154	41.55 -27.55	"
16092	restart P7			41.38 -27.42	ascending over small c (1/8) further small c above (2/8) above that station
16102					
161002		500 ^{Pres} ^{Rad} ^{FL}			
161452		50 ^{Pres} ^{Rad} ^{FL}		41.12 -27.22	Above 2/8 station deck. Sub. from cloud above / cirrus
161814				40.97 -27.06	just in cloud top
161827	restart P7	 ^{Pres} ^{Rad} ^{FL}		40.96 -27.08	ascending over station deck above above

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: RICHER

Project: ACSOE
Flight No: A579

Date: 20/09/97
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
162356	Interupt	110 Pres Rad FL	149	40.72 -26.78	ozone increases up to this level (up to 50 ppb)
162635		Pres Rad FL			stratocum below us now broken
162710	Restart P7	110 Pres Rad FL	148	40.58 -26.6	Now mostly over clear sea 4/8 upper / mid level cloud above.
163054		50 Pres Rad FL		40.35 -26.34	NOy increases to Max at about FC130
163534	Restart P7	110 Pres Rad FL		40.17 -26.4	2/8 small cum below, some stratiform cloud above
164025	Interupt	200 Pres Rad FL		39.92 -25.84	2/8 cloud (altocum.) above some cirrus
164432	Restart	200 Pres Rad FL		39.70 -25.63	lenticula cloud from islands seen
165236	Restart run 5	200 Pres Rad FL	148	37.01 -25.00	Little flr NOy 0.35, O3 58
165639	P8	200 Pres Rad FL		39.00 -24.92	Normal en route descent to FL100. Cirrus above variable cloud below - none directly below at 2000 feet/min (last 1000 feet)
170520	Run 6	Pres Rad FL			

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. AS79 Date: 20/9/97 User: NERC
Interactive by: Dave Tiddeman
Date: 8/10/97

Renav

Kalman Filtering

TWC

Profile plotted: No

Line chosen: Profile / Whole flight / Other

$$a = -2.247$$

$$b = +0.3527 \times 10^{-2}$$

$$c = +0.2276 \times 10^{-6}$$

LWC

OK (no PMS data)

Heimann / Barnes

OK

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A579

Date: 20/9/07

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	<u>0567</u>			Approx	0568
	REF -	7	<u>2853</u>			Approx	2858
	AOSS	19	<u>0000</u>	F/S O/S	TORQUE <u>4-5</u>	2047 st.	and level
	AOA	18	<u>4057</u>	F/S O/S	TORQUE <u>3-5</u>	2047 st.	and level
	RD HT	37	<u>0200</u>	✓		As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	<u>3828</u>	<u>0.00</u> ✓		As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	<u>3328</u>	<u>1020</u> ✓			
	A/S	9	<u>0004</u>	✓		As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	<u>0042</u>		JOID		
	UP2S	82	<u>0205</u>				
	UIRS	83	<u>0258</u>		JNO2		
	UP1Z	84	<u>0240</u>		JOID	Approx	0147
	UP2Z	85	<u>0144</u>	✓		Approx	0149
	UIRZ	86	<u>0232</u>		JNO2	Approx	2061
	UP1T	87	<u>0492</u>		JOID	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	<u>2370</u>	<u>21</u>		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	<u>0000</u>		JNO2	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	<u>0030</u>		JOID		
	LP2S	92	<u>0140</u>				
	LIRS	93	<u>0011</u>		JNO2		
	LP1Z	94	<u>0223</u>		JOID	Approx	0150
	LP2Z	95	<u>0149</u>	✓		Approx	0146
	LIRZ	96	<u>0011</u>		JNO2	Approx	2050
	LP1T	97	<u>0000</u>		JOID	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	<u>2352</u>	<u>21</u>		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	<u>0200</u>		JNO2	As IAT	
	J/W	42	<u>0046</u>	<u>0</u> ✓		As Indicated	0000
	HYGR	58	<u>0154</u>	<u>22</u>			
	HYCC	59	<u>0707</u>			696-901	
	FDEW	138	<u>2223</u>	<u>11</u>		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	<u>0608</u>				
	DTF	10	<u>2076</u>	<u>24</u>			
	DTC	11	<u>6</u>				
	NDTF	23	<u>1768</u>	<u>23</u>		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	<u>6</u>				
	INCT	48	<u>2739</u>				
	HEIM	141	<u>2652</u>				
	PRTC	142	<u>2384</u>	✓		approx	2380
	TWCD	70	<u>1605</u>			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	<u>0680</u>	✓		0640-1860	< min
	O3	100	<u>0000</u>				
	O3P	106	<u>2059</u>			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	<u>1748</u>				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	579			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0290			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0543			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	7			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3766	3856	3764	0485	3766	3689	3768	0137
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONG	161	Dec	4094			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 0

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	4095	4095	4095 ✓	0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	4095	4095	1225 ✓	2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0485	0485	0192 ✓	0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	1746	NOV	2546 ✓	2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	1007	1007	2154 ✓	2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2054	2054	2054 ✓	0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2115	2115	2115 ✓	0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1023	1023	1023 ✓	0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78			4095	4095	
	EV1V	170			2023		
	EV2V	171			2043		
	NPWR	172			3352		
	EVIC	173			3968		
	EV2C	174			3968		

was 1900

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear (J11)	(Off) / On	Large / (Small)
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon (J11)		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear (J11)	(Off) / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon (J11)		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 579.....

Date 20/9/97.....

Page 1 of 2.....

Video Tape	
No. A579 #1	Ends 1411
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	36° 58' 40" N	36° 58' 30" N
Long	025° 09' 48" W	025° 09' 46" W
Time	0848	0849
Status	5's	GL ALGN

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
0828				DATA	ON				
105850				SET	INU TO NAV				
110242				T/O	SANTA MARIA				
111107	9			START	VIDEO A STAFF #1				COUNT = 0000
				START	RUN 1				
111449	10	ALTO		080					
112746	11	FL70		080	END RUN 1				
113416	12	50'	1026	075	START P1				SS=4
115102	13	FL90		075	INTERUPT P1				INSTRUMENT ZERO'S
115422	14	FL90		355	RESUME P1				
120941	15	FL70		355	END P1 / START PUN 2				BOTTLE FILL FL70 200 130 70 300 50
121709	16	FL70		355	START P2 / END RUN 2				
122407	17	FL30		355	INTERUPT P2				BOTTLE FILL
122347	18	FL70		355	RESUME P2				
122452	19	FL70		355	INTERUPT P2				ZERO'S BOTTLES
123324	20	FL70		355	RESUME P2				
123756	22	3000'		355	INTERUPT P2				BOTTLE FILL
123950	23	3000'		355	RESUME P2				↓ 500'/min
124359	24	500'		355	INTERUPT P2				
124538	25	500'		355	RESUME P2				
124648	26	50'	1023	360	END P2 / START P3				SS=5
124706	27	100'		355	INTERUPT P3				BOTTLE FILL
124916	28	100'		350	RESUME P3				3000' FL70
125204	29	3000'		355	INTERUPT P3				BOTTLE FILL FL70, FL50
125420	30	3000'		350	RESUME P3				FL40

Video Tape	
No.	A579#1
Ends	1411
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	41° 53' 53" N	42° 15' 33" N
Long	023° 09' 26" W	023° 16' 13" W
Time	1258	1304
Status	5's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
125843	31	FL70		355	INTERLUPT P3		- BOTTLE FILL		100 5000 FL70, F150
130233	32	FL70		355	RESSTART P3				F140 F110
130522	33	FL100			INTERLUPT P3				
130752	34	FL100		0245	RESSTART P3			(4) 44-00-0	
131324	35	FL150		0240	INTERLUPT P3			22-00-0	
131703	36	FL150		0240	RESSTART P3				
132946	37	FL220			INTERLUPT P3		- REPOSITION		
133228	38	FL220		215	RESSTART P3				
133530	39	FL240		225	END P3		- BOTTLE FILL / START RUN 3		
134009	40	FL240		280	END RUN 3 / START P4				P20
134241	41	FL240		280	INTERLUPT P4		- BOTTLE FILL		
134543	42	FL244		280	RESSTART P4				
134717	43	FL200		280	INTERLUPT P4		- BOTTLE FILL		
135044	44	FL200		280	RESSTART P4				
135623	45	FL150		295	INTERLUPT P4		- BOTTLE FILL		
135938	46	FL150		295	RESSTART P4				
140352	47	FL110		295	INTERLUPT P4		- BOTTLE FILL		
140713	48	FL110		295	RESSTART P4				
141361	51	FL150		305	INTERLUPT P4		- BOTTLE FILL		
141121	49				STOP VIDEO A579#1		COUNT = 0071		
141212	50				START VIDEO A579#2		COUNT = 0000		
141557	52	FL150		295	RESSTART P4				
142364	53	500'		295	INTERLUPT P4		- BOTTLE FILL		
142544	54	500'		290	RESSTART P4				
142645	55	50'	1017		END P4 / START P5		SE=14		100 5000 FL110 F150 FL200 F140
142701	56	100'		295	INTERLUPT P5		- BOTTLE FILL		
142901	57	100'		295	RESSTART P5				
143412	58	FL150		295	INTERLUPT P5		- BOTTLE FILL		
143725	59	FL150		20200	RESSTART P5				
144336	60	FL110		280	INTERLUPT P5		- BOTTLE FILL		
144402	61	FL110		280	RESSTART P5				
145033	62	FL150		290	INTERLUPT P5		- BOTTLE FILL		
145400	63	FL150		280	RESSTART P5				
150514	65	FL200		275	INTERLUPT P5		- BOTTLE FILL		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 579.....

Date 20/9/98.....

Page 2 of 2

Video Tape	
No.	A579#2
Ends	1712
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	43 46.35N	43 42.15N
Long	029 40.48	29 36.84W
Time	1521	1522
Status	S's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y	n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y	n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y	n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
150325	66	FL260		275	RESTART P6				
151523	67	FL260		270	RESTART P6 P5 END / START PUN 4				
151822	68	FL260		165	END PUN 4 / START P6 ↓				
152454	69	FL200		170	INTERUPT P6			BOTTLE FILL	200 150 200 100 500
152820	70	FL200		170	RESTART P6				
153604	71	FL150		170	INTERUPT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
153722	72	FL150		170	RESTART P6				
153835	73	FL130		170	INTERUPT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
15443	74	FL130		170	RESTART P6				
154511	75	FL110		170	INTERUPT P6			BOTTLE FILL, ZERO'S	
154908	76	FL110		170	RESTART P6				
155458	77	FL150		170	INTERUPT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
155655	78	FL150		170	RESTART P6				500 / 1000
160204	80	500'		170	INTERUPT P6			BOTTLE FILL	
160412	81	500'		170	RESTART P6				
160509	82	50'	1018	170	END P6 / START P7 MAX				SS = 4
160524	83	100'	1018	170	INTERUPT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
160822	84	100'			RESTART P7				
161602	85	FL150		170	INTERUPT P7			BOTTLE FILL	ZERO'S
161827	86	FL150		170	RESTART P7				
162356	87	FL110		165	INTERUPT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
162710	88	FL110		165	RESTART P7				
163054	89	FL150		165	INTERUPT P7			BOTTLE FILL	
163524	90	FL150		160	RESTART P7				
164025	91	FL200		160	INTERUPT P7			BOTTLE FILL	ZERO'S
164432	92	FL200		160	RESTART P7				
165236	93	FL260		160	END P7 / START PUN 5			BOTTLE FILL	
165639	94	FL260		165	END PUN 5 / START P8				

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

light No. A579

Date 19 9 97

Sheet no. 1/3

Sample No.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
1	R3	121250		FL 170	120900	121250	121453	527	6.2 bar RUN 2 ON P1
2	B51	122221		130	¹²²¹⁰⁷ 121900	122221	122338	622	7 bar P2
3	R12			070	¹²²⁹⁵² 122700	123239	123314	784	7 bar P2
4	R27			3000	¹²³⁷⁵² 123430	123905	123927	923	7 bar P2
5	P3 B1			500	¹²⁴³⁵⁷ 124200	124510	124529	1009	7 bar P2
6	Z10			500	¹²⁴⁷⁰⁶ 124628	124830	124903	1021	7 bar P3
7	B53			3000	¹²⁵²⁰⁴ 125100	125340	125410	919	7 bar P3
8	Z11			FL 070	125849 125500	130150	130225	785	7 bar P3 500 3000 070
9	A8			FL 100	¹³⁰⁵²² 130330	130700	130741	690	7 bar P3 100 130
0	R15			FL 150	131330 130830	131610	131755	575	6 bar P3
1	Z12	X		FL 240	133120 132800		133950	395	4.4 RUN 3 P4
1	Z12			FL 214	134200	134413	134535	439	4.8 P4 200 150
2	R26			FL 200	¹³⁴¹¹⁷ 134000	134856	135036	466	5.0 P4 400 5000
3	R14			FL 150	135223 135230	135805	135935	573	6.4 P4 500
4	H08			FL 110	¹⁴⁰³⁵² 140130	140633	140739	671	7 bar P4
5	#12			FL 050	141351 140500	141505	141550	-	7 bar P4
6	Z13			500	¹⁴²³⁵⁰ 141700	142517	142542	1002	7 bar P4
7	Z14			FL 100	1427	142810	142857	1016	7 bar P5 500 500
8	#3			FL 100	¹⁴³³⁴² 143000	143648	143722	846	7 bar P5 100 150
9	P3 B3			FL 110	144346 144035	144529	144615	671	7 bar P5 200 200
0	HAR 7			FL 150	144800	145215	145400	574	6.7 bar P5 200

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

1111

light No. A579 Date 20/9/97 Sheet no. 2/3

Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
				PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
21	P3		FL	150014		150321	466	5 bar
	B4		200	145530	1450145			P5
2	Z		FL	151323				
	15		260	150455	151546	151758	362	3.95 bar RUN 4
3	Z		FL	152454				
	16		200	151900	152638	152815	465	5 bar P6
4	Z		FL	153404				
	17		150	153000	153535	153720	524	5 bar P6
5	Z		FL	153935				
	18		130	153031	154145	154310	621	7 bar P6
6	R		FL	154511				
	18		110		154000	154903	674	7 bar P6
7	VER		FL	155458				
	D*		50	155100	155600	155631	846	MAX PRESS 40 PSI * 2.7 bar P6
8	VER		FL	160204				
	G*		500'	160000	160345	160408	1002	2.7 bar P6
9	N140		FL	160524				
	317		100'	160524	160755	160815	1017	4.5 bar P7
0	N140		FL	161402				
	408		50		161700	161737	844	4.5 bar P8
1	N140		FL	162356				
	320		110	161930	162622	162705	670	4.5 bar 501615200 P8
2	N		FL	163050				
	307		150	1628	163200	163523	573	4.5 bar 260

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: AS79					Operator: <i>Joos Kern</i>					Date: <i>20/9/97</i>			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = <i>13</i>					Optimisation = <i>8</i>				Optimisation = <i>12</i>				
			Back Flush = <i>44</i>					Back Flush = <i>43</i>				Back Flush = <i>45</i>				<i>Good Optimisation</i>
			Flow rate = <i>42</i>					Flow rate = <i>41</i>				Flow rate = <i>41</i>				
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP	
<i>1</i>	<i>112250</i>	<i>FL80</i>	<i>485</i>	<i>1219</i>				<i>515</i>	<i>1468</i>			<i>481</i>	<i>1538</i>			
<i>2</i>	<i>115050</i>	<i>FL90</i>	<i>470</i>	<i>1150</i>				<i>504</i>	<i>1455</i>			<i>469</i>	<i>1416</i>			
<i>3</i>	<i>115652</i>	<i>FL110</i>	<i>468</i>	<i>1106</i>				<i>502</i>	<i>1404</i>			<i>467</i>	<i>1367</i>			
<i>4</i>	<i>120304</i>	<i>FL140</i>	<i>464</i>	<i>1022</i>				<i>501</i>	<i>1300</i>			<i>466</i>	<i>1266</i>			
<i>5</i>	<i>120852</i>	<i>FL170</i>	<i>465</i>	<i>909</i>				<i>500</i>	<i>1195</i>			<i>465</i>	<i>1176</i>			
<i>6</i>	<i>122129</i>	<i>FL130</i>	<i>464</i>	<i>1061</i>				<i>500</i>	<i>1348</i>			<i>466</i>	<i>1332</i>			
<i>7</i>	<i>123025</i>	<i>FL70</i>	<i>462</i>	<i>1252</i>				<i>499</i>	<i>1621</i>			<i>466</i>	<i>1584</i>			
<i>8</i>	<i>123812</i>	<i>3000'</i>	<i>461</i>	<i>1393</i>				<i>498</i>	<i>1812</i>			<i>465</i>	<i>1954</i>			
<i>9</i>	<i>124406</i>	<i>500'</i>	<i>460</i>	<i>1468</i>				<i>498</i>	<i>1836</i>			<i>465</i>	<i>1832</i>			
<i>10</i>	<i>125228</i>	<i>3000'</i>	<i>460</i>	<i>1372</i>				<i>496</i>	<i>1773</i>			<i>466</i>	<i>1674</i>			
<i>11</i>	<i>125910</i>	<i>FL70</i>	<i>461</i>	<i>1223</i>				<i>499</i>	<i>1556</i>			<i>467</i>	<i>1519</i>			
<i>12</i>	<i>130534</i>	<i>FL100</i>	<i>465</i>	<i>1140</i>				<i>499</i>	<i>1465</i>			<i>469</i>	<i>1627</i>			

DATE 20 SEP 97	FTI No 01	FLT No A 579	NAV AMERS
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD SANTA MARIA	ATIS 16 210/06 10K 22/22 1023		
ATC CLEARANCE <i>EEKOR</i>		38/22 44/24 44/30 38/24 DELTA	TAKE OFF TIME 1102

X3500 TAKEOFF (FL170.) 220/12

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1114 ⁴⁹	070	0	224	183	212	229/16	F080	1023	3702.5	02428.0	R1
1127 ⁴⁶									3720.2	02331.5	ER1
1134 ¹⁶	061	2P	192	182	196	173/18	50'f	1026	3733.2	02307.0	P1
1151 ⁰²							F090		3759.0	02201.4	IP1
1154 ²²							F090		3809.7	02200.1	RP1
1209 ⁴¹							F170		3905.1	02216.2	IP1/R2
1217 ⁰⁹							F170		3934.0	02224.9	ER2/P2
1221 ⁰⁷							F130		3949.1	02229.3	IP2
1229 ⁵²							F070		4020.4	02237.4	IP2
1237 ⁵⁶	341	4S	206	184	196	208/13	3000	1026	4048.0	02246.6	IP2
1243 ⁵⁹							500		4108.2	02253.3	IP2
1246 ⁴⁸						161/15	50'f ¹⁰⁰		4117.4	02256.4	EP2/P3
1252 ⁰⁴							3000		4134.7	02302.8	IP3
1258 ⁴³							F070		4157.0	02310.4	IP3
1305 ²²							F100		4220.5	02318.4	IP3
1313 ²⁴							F150		4248.7	02259.4	IP3
1329 ⁴⁶							F220		4349.2	02207.0	IP3
1332 ²⁸	2						F220		4344.7	02201.5	RP3
1335 ⁵⁰	212	6P	238	174	259	258/36	F240		4332.5	02209.8	EP3/R3
1340 ⁰⁹	271	0	247	184	269	268/33	F240		4321.1	02224.2	ER3/P4
1347 ¹⁷							F214 F200		4322.0	02302.8	IP4
1356 ²³							F150		4330.1	02349.8	IP4
1403 ⁵²							F110		4338.0	02425.3	IP4
1413 ⁴¹							F050		4349.3	02508.8	IP4
1423 ⁴⁹							500'	10	4358.9	02549.4	IP4

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	TAKE OFF
ATIS	FLIGHT TIME

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV <i>Ayers</i>
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD		ATIS	
ATC CLEARANCE			TAKE OFF TIME <i>1100</i>

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH 1020	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
<i>1426⁴</i>							<i>505</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>4400.7</i>	<i>02601.0</i>	<i>EP4/P5</i>
<i>1434¹⁰</i>							<i>F050</i>		<i>4405.8</i>	<i>02631.1</i>	<i>IP5</i>
<i>1442³²</i>	<i>268</i>	<i>7S</i>	<i>200</i>	<i>181</i>	<i>219</i>	<i>219/30</i>	<i>F110</i>		<i>4405.0</i>	<i>02710.7</i>	<i>IP5</i>
<i>1450³³</i>							<i>F150</i>		<i>4406.0</i>	<i>02742.8</i>	<i>IP5</i>
<i>1500¹⁴</i>							<i>F200</i>		<i>4405.8</i>	<i>02826.8</i>	<i>IP5</i>
<i>1513²³</i>							<i>F260</i>		<i>4402.2</i>	<i>02932.8</i>	<i>EP5/R4</i>
<i>1518²²</i>	<i>152</i>	<i>10P</i>	<i>273</i>				<i>F260x</i>		<i>4354.5</i>	<i>02950.7</i>	<i>EP4/P6</i>
<i>1524⁵⁴</i>	<i>154</i>	<i>8P</i>	<i>243</i>	<i>180</i>	<i>249</i>	<i>234/44</i>	<i>F200</i>		<i>4332.9</i>	<i>02925.9</i>	<i>IP6</i>
<i>1534⁰⁴</i>							<i>F150</i>		<i>4303.1</i>	<i>02854.8</i>	<i>IP6</i>
<i>1539³⁵</i>							<i>F130</i>		<i>4246.5</i>	<i>02837.3</i>	<i>IP6</i>
<i>1545¹¹</i>							<i>F110</i>		<i>4230.0</i>	<i>02821.1</i>	<i>IP6</i>
<i>1554⁵⁸</i>							<i>F050</i>		<i>4202.3</i>	<i>02754.5</i>	<i>IP6</i>
<i>1602⁰⁴</i>	<i>154</i>	<i>3P</i>	<i>181</i>	<i>181</i>	<i>187</i>	<i>234/15</i>	<i>500</i>		<i>4142.8</i>	<i>02738.3</i>	<i>IP6</i>
<i>1605⁰⁹</i>							<i>500</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>4134.6</i>	<i>02732.0</i>	<i>EP6/P7</i>
<i>1614⁰²</i>							<i>F050</i>		<i>4110.4</i>	<i>02712.7</i>	<i>IP7</i>
<i>1623⁵⁶</i>							<i>F110</i>		<i>4044.4</i>	<i>02645.0</i>	<i>IP7</i>
<i>1630⁵⁹</i>							<i>F150</i>		<i>4024.6</i>	<i>02622.7</i>	<i>IP7</i>
<i>1640³⁵</i>							<i>F200</i>		<i>3957.2</i>	<i>02552.1</i>	<i>IP7</i>
<i>1652⁵⁴</i>	<i>150</i>	<i>7P</i>	<i>250</i>	<i>156</i>	<i>245</i>	<i>248/35</i>	<i>F260</i>		<i>3916.8</i>	<i>02509.3</i>	<i>IP7/P5</i>
<i>1656³⁹</i>							<i>F260</i>		<i>3902.0</i>	<i>02455.1</i>	<i>EP5/P8</i>
<i>1705²⁰</i>	<i>152</i>	<i>7P</i>	<i>207</i>	<i>180</i>	<i>218</i>	<i>238/23</i>	<i>F100</i>		<i>3825.0</i>	<i>02424.1</i>	<i>IP8/P8</i>

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME <i>1750</i>
ATC CLEARANCES	TAKE OFF <i>1100</i>
ATIS # <i>1022. 4W18 200/19 101C 25/</i>	FLIGHT TIME <i>650</i>

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: *A579*

DATE: *20 1 9 197*

MRF *1 Aesde*

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION:			
GPS	✓	✓	
OMEGA	✓	✓	
INU	✓	✓	
RADALT	✓	✓	
THERMOMETERS:			
DI TEMP	✓	✓	
NDI TEMP	✓	✓	
ICTP	✓	✓	
HEIMANN			
HYGROMETERS:			
GEN. EASTERN	✓	✓	
TWC	✓	✓	
FWVS	✓	✓	
J/W	✓	✓	
EXP. PITOT HEAD:			
STATIC PRESS.	✓	✓	
PITOT PRESS.	✓	✓	
GUST VANES	✓	✓	
RADIOMETERS:			
UPPER CLEAR	✓	✓	<i>JO'D</i>
UPPER RED	✓	✓	
UPPER SILICON	✓	✓	<i>JNO₂</i>
LOWER CLEAR	✓	✓	<i>JO'D</i>
LOWER RED	✓	✓	
LOWER SILICON	✓	✓	<i>JNO₂</i>
MARSS	✗		
SAFIRE	✗		
DEIMOS	✗		
ARIES	✗		
CHEMISTRY:			
OZONE	✓	✓	
ECGC	✓	✓	
NOX	✓	✓	
OTHERS:			
CCN	✗		
CLOUD PHYSICS	✗		
CABIN PRESS	✓	✓	
NEPHELOMETER	✓	✓	
PSAP	✓	✓	

A579

GPS data
08:05:09 - 17:50:31

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet ✓ Aircraft Scientist log ✓ Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form ✓ Flight Leader in-flight log ✓ Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log <i>bottles, etc</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log ✓ Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots ✓ Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

ASXX EGR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 20 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallels 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

20 SEP '97 03:45

MET-OFFICE_ARTIFAX_3 ** TOTAL PAGE: 001 ** MET-OFFICE OFFICE FAX F 28

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 20 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Dist. Scale 1:20M

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS

70:	50	25	10
60:	40	20	10
50:	30	15	10
40:	20	10	10

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

70:	100	200	300	400	500	600	700
60:	100	200	300	400	500	600	700
50:	100	200	300	400	500	600	700
40:	100	200	300	400	500	600	700

Prepared and drawn in the Cartographic Section, MATS 0188, Division, MATS/CENTCOM/COMNAVSTA, Amphibious Air Base

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 21 SEP 1997

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 28

** TOTAL PAGE 001 ** MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_5 PAGE. 001

20 SEP '97 05:01

FS/FUXX EGRR

Printed on Demand by the Cartographic Section, MFLD 1018, 4111 Aveil
Met. Office (D.O. Form 610/81) 10/1987
11
Printed in Great Britain by HMSO for HMSO by GPO 1987

FS/FUXX EGRR

POL. STER. PROJ. STAND. PARALLEL 60°N 0 500 1000 NM SEA LEVEL ISOPLETHS 1000-500 mb THICKNESS ISOPLETHS

ASXN EGRR SURFACE DT 0000 UTC 20 SEP 1997 97408

PAGE.001

TO 4806

20 SEP '97 06:29 FROM MET ITOPS BRACKNELL

** TOTAL PAGE.001 **
MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4 PAGE.001 **

20 SEP '97 07:02

Approved and issued by the Controller of the Air, G. 113 (aerodrome) and G. 114 (en route) charts. (Aeronautical Information Manual)

DI 00Z SAT 20/ 9/97 VT. 00Z SAT 20/ 9/97 GMAIN T+ 0 HEIGHT DM. 300MB

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.30.46 CHART 27 [PHDA30 EGRR 0000Z

DT 00Z SAT 20/ 9/97 VT 00Z SUN 21/ 9/97 GRAIN I + 24 HEIGHT DM. 300MB

MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX-3 PAGE. 001

20 SEP . 97 04:01

CHART 27 PHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:38.29

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.31.01

CHART 27

PHDA50 EGRR 0000Z

20 SEP '97 04:04

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

500-1000MB
500MB

T + 24
GMAIN

21/ 9/97
VT 00Z SUN

20/ 9/97
DT 00Z SAT

588

PHDE50 EGRR 000Z
CHART 27
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:38.45

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

DT 00Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

.03 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VT

T+0 VT OZ SATURDAY 20/9/1997

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

DT 00Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997 LMRIN

SNOW
CONNECTIVE
DYNAMIC
: .03 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VI

T+12 VI 12Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

DT 00Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

.05 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VT

20 SEP 97 03:38

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4

PAGE. 001

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
 TOTAL PPN RATE
 PRESSURE AT MSL
 01 00Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997 LMJN
 DYNAMIC
 CONNECTIVE
 SNOW
 .03 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VT

1+36 VI 122 SUNDAY 21/9/1997 38

TOTAL ACCUMULATION
850MB MET BUFB POT TEMP DT 12Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997

RAINFALL IN MM DURING THE 6 HOURS ENDING AT VT

T+24 VI 12Z SUNDAY 21/9/1997
T+30 VI 18Z SUNDAY 21/9/1997
T+36 VI 0Z MONDAY 22/9/1997

20 SEP '97 02:40

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4 PAGE. 001

SNO
 CONNECTIVE
 DYNAMIC
 .03
 .1
 .5
 1.0
 NM/HR AT VT
 *
 *
 *

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
 TOTAL PPN RATE
 PRESSURE AT MSL
 DT 00Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL

TOTAL PPN RATE

PRESSURE AT MSL

01 12Z SATURDAY 20/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW
CONNECTIVE
DYNAMIC
MM/HR AT VT
-03 -1 .5 1.0

99317

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 050

VALID 12 UTC 20 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 19 SEP 97

EGRR 12007

99314

99316

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 100

VALID 12 UTC 20 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'P.'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 19 SEP 97

ECRR 1200Z

99315

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 180

VALID 12 UTC 20 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'P.'
ONIA TIME 12 UTC 19 SEP 97

FORM 1200Z

99313

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 300

VALID 12 UTC 20 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY °FS.
DATA TIME 12 UTC 19 SEP 97

EORR 12007

STATION: 08509	
LAJES (ACORES)	
TIME: 200000 +12 9EP 87	
mb	Deg Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL	
150	245 28
201	255 29
252	246 34
303	250 37
359	250 32
428	250 27
513	245 24
611	250 16
713	230 16
808	220 21
888	220 20
949	220 19
995	215 15
1017	215 13
Parts: A C D missing	

STATION: 08509
 LAJES (ACORES)
 TIME: 200000 +24 SEP 97

mb	deg	Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL		
150	260	30
201	245	37
252	240	27
303	245	40
359	235	33
428	230	37
513	235	33
610	236	27
713	235	23
808	230	20
887	230	15
949	230	13
994	220	12
1017	220	11

Parts: A C D missing

STATION: 08509	
LAJES (ACORES)	
TIME: 200000 +36 SEP 97	
mb	Deg Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL	
150	225 29
201	220 39
252	225 46
303	225 51
359	230 48
428	230 39
513	230 30
611	235 23
714	245 20
809	240 17
888	270 12
950	295 10
995	305 9
1018	305 8
Parts : A C D missing	

A579 20-SEP-97

P1 50'-FL170 (113416-120941) + P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500'(121709-124648)

A578 20-SEP-97

P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL70/FL100/FL150/FL240(124648-133550) + P4 FL240-50' R/FL214/FL200/FL150/FL110/FL50/500'(134009-142645)

A579 20-SEP-97
P6 50' FL260 R/100'/FL150/FL110/FL200(142645-151323) + P6 FL260-50' R/FL200/FL150/FL130/FL110/FL150/500'(151822-160509)

A578 20-SEP-97

P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200(160509-165236) + P8 FL260-FL100 (165639-170520)

A579 20-SEP-97 R1 FL80

From 111449-112746 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:26

A579 20-SEP-97 R1 FL80

From 111449-112746 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:26

A579 20-SEP-97 R1 FL80

From 111449-112746 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:26

A579 20-SEP-97 R1 FL80

From 111449-112746 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:26

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 778
 Mean 753.487
 Standard dev 0.269563
 Max value 754.566
 Min value 752.813

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 778
 Mean 282.027
 Standard dev 0.197520
 Max value 282.468
 Min value 281.266

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 778
 Mean 278.321
 Standard dev 1.30764
 Max value 280.031
 Min value 272.440

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 778
 Mean 35.9164
 Standard dev 3.52234
 Max value 46.3748
 Min value 30.2248

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 778
 Mean 1.000000e-38
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 1.000000e-38
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 778
 Mean 12.3179
 Standard dev 2.20167
 Max value 17.2842
 Min value 7.43844

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 778
 Mean 2429.22
 Standard dev 2.85182
 Max value 2436.36
 Min value 2417.81

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 778
 Mean 37.1969
 Standard dev 8.482909e-02
 Max value 37.3389
 Min value 37.0434

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 778
 Mean -23.9970
 Standard dev 0.274840
 Max value -23.5219
 Min value -24.4650

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 778
 Mean 5.36087
 Standard dev 0.690231
 Max value 6.65119
 Min value 3.64623

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 778
 Mean 6.97660
 Standard dev 0.943901
 Max value 8.77902
 Min value 4.85733

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 778
 Mean -0.129385
 Standard dev 0.416251
 Max value 0.489784
 Min value -1.81758

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 778
 Mean 8.85466
 Standard dev 0.610672
 Max value 10.1213
 Min value 7.37304

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 232.461

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 778
 Mean 107.002
 Standard dev 1.54991
 Max value 110.486
 Min value 103.822

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 68.6195

A579 20-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL170 From 113416-120941 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:39

A579 20-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL170 From 113416-120941 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:40

A579 20-SEP-97 P1 50'-FL170 From 113416-120941 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:40

A579 20-SEP-97 R2 FL170 From 120941-121709 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:43

A579 20-SEP-97 R2 FL170 From 120941-121709 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:43

A579 20-SEP-97 R2 FL170 From 120941-121709 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:43

A579 20-SEP-97 R2 FL170 From 120941-121709 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:43

A579 20-SEP-97 R2 FL170

From 120941-121709 Plotted 7-May-1998 09:43

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 449
Mean 528.081
Standard dev 0.678290
Max value 529.076
Min value 525.498

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 449
Mean 266.198
Standard dev 0.152020
Max value 266.553
Min value 265.909

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 449
Mean 245.323
Standard dev 1.42470
Max value 247.072
Min value 240.637

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 449
Mean 66.9371
Standard dev 1.65343
Max value 70.7645
Min value 62.8219

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 449
Mean 1.000000e-38
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1.000000e-38
Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 449
Mean 12.6943
Standard dev 0.110677
Max value 12.9199
Min value 12.5361

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 449
Mean 5169.33
Standard dev 9.58385
Max value 5205.84
Min value 5155.30

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 449
Mean 39.3284
Standard dev 0.139074
Max value 39.5686
Min value 39.0881

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 449
Mean -22.3457
Standard dev 4.090567e-02
Max value -22.2731
Min value -22.4155

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 449
Mean -1.73856
Standard dev 0.403111
Max value -0.750267
Min value -2.43789

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 449
Mean 5.16296
Standard dev 0.985123
Max value 7.21850
Min value 3.27969

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 449
Mean -0.475955
Standard dev 0.390042
Max value 8.026123e-02
Min value -1.29450

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 449
Mean 5.48402
Standard dev 0.858136
Max value 7.51529
Min value 3.95507

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 288.610

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 449
Mean 124.847
Standard dev 1.01342
Max value 128.830
Min value 122.974

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 347.038

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

A579 20-SEP-97 P2 FL170-50' R/FL130/FL70/3000'/500' From 121709-124648 Plotted 7-May-1998

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1780
Mean 788.494
Standard dev 147.804
Max value 1020.44
Min value 528.346

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1780
Mean 282.271
Standard dev 7.79385
Max value 294.035
Min value 266.283

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1780
Mean 272.489
Standard dev 15.0614
Max value 291.655
Min value 241.344

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1780
Mean 41.0413
Standard dev 16.6543
Max value 72.5142
Min value 16.6566

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 1780
Mean 3.765755e-08
Standard dev 4.202510e-07
Max value 6.385480e-06
Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 1780
Mean 11.1289
Standard dev 0.927801
Max value 12.7113
Min value 8.80133

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1780
Mean 2183.30
Standard dev 1536.45
Max value 5165.60
Min value -59.6528

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1780
Mean 40.4540
Standard dev 0.495183
Max value 41.2934
Min value 39.5686

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1780
Mean -22.6736
Standard dev 0.150441
Max value -22.4155
Min value -22.9411

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1780
Mean 4.43962
Standard dev 3.12891
Max value 10.5274
Min value -0.818657

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1780
Mean 3.14183
Standard dev 3.24509
Max value 8.29629
Min value -2.68295

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1780
Mean 0.361670
Standard dev 0.429574
Max value 1.35368
Min value -0.593346

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1780
Mean 6.82249
Standard dev 1.82921
Max value 10.5281
Min value 2.78699

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 215.286

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1780
Mean 106.726
Standard dev 8.60140
Max value 125.183
Min value 91.5194

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 346.900

A579 20-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL70/FL100/FL150/FL240 From 124648-133550 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL70/FL100/FL150/FL240 From 124648-133550 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL70/FL150/FL240 From 124648-133550 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL150/FL100/FL70/FL240 From 124648-133550 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL100/FL150/FL240 From 124648-133550 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL70/FL100/FL150/FL240 From 124648-133550 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P3 50'-FL240 R/100'/3000'/FL150/FL100/FL70/FL240 From 124648-133550 Plotted

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 658.008
 Standard dev 188.894
 Max value 1020.44
 Min value 394.001

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 272.429
 Standard dev 13.1909
 Max value 294.035
 Min value 248.785

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 267.470
 Standard dev 12.8297
 Max value 291.590
 Min value 245.529

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 41.7009
 Standard dev 9.53626
 Max value 66.1196
 Min value 26.2781

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2943
 Mean 5.474324e-09
 Standard dev 8.467210e-08
 Max value 2.209204e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 13.0710
 Standard dev 2.12915
 Max value 17.2207
 Min value 6.14791

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 3752.47
 Standard dev 2216.53
 Max value 7291.96
 Min value -59.6528

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 42.6732
 Standard dev 0.790040
 Max value 43.8549
 Min value 41.2934

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2943
 Mean -22.8153
 Standard dev 0.417949
 Max value -21.9841
 Min value -23.3168

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 7.92622
 Standard dev 2.40812
 Max value 12.9006
 Min value 1.56428

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 7.44814
 Standard dev 4.48341
 Max value 18.4964
 Min value -2.85857

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2943
 Mean -0.619025
 Standard dev 0.524157
 Max value 1.19539
 Min value -1.62954

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 11.7659
 Standard dev 2.39917
 Max value 18.8962
 Min value 6.63241

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 223.219

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2943
 Mean 114.672
 Standard dev 13.3662
 Max value 145.096
 Min value 92.8864

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 14.0624

A579 20-SEP-97 R3 FL240

From 133550-134009 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:11

A579 20-SEP-97 R3 FL240 From 133550-134009 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:11

A579 20-SEP-97 R3 FL240

From 133550-134009 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:11

A579 20-SEP-97 R3 FL240

From 133550-134009 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:11

A579 20-SEP-97 P4 FL240-50' R/FL214/FL200/FL150/FL110/FL50/500' From 134009-142645 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P4 FL240-50' R/FL214/FL200/FL150/FL110/FL50/500' From 134009-142645 *Plotted*

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2795
Mean 670.943
Standard dev 190.135
Max value 1015.29
Min value 393.872

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2795
Mean 272.872
Standard dev 12.8114
Max value 292.809
Min value 248.984

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2795
Mean 269.870
Standard dev 13.9094
Max value 291.406
Min value 248.582

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2795
Mean 40.1901
Standard dev 6.22813
Max value 55.5115
Min value 1.000000e-38

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2795
Mean 2.820765e-07
Standard dev 8.577042e-07
Max value 5.066657e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 2795
Mean 12.9321
Standard dev 3.45515
Max value 24.3381
Min value 3.04958

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2795
Mean 3598.47
Standard dev 2213.18
Max value 7294.28
Min value -16.9650

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2795
Mean 43.6198
Standard dev 1.16404
Max value 44.0132
Min value -16.7734

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2795
Mean -24.3215
Standard dev 1.14126
Max value 0.330634
Min value -26.0195

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2795
Mean 7.03786
Standard dev 2.62767
Max value 60.3088
Min value 0.493263

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2795
Mean 8.73682
Standard dev 3.25110
Max value 116.090
Min value 2.96931

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2795
Mean 0.316579
Standard dev 4.08685
Max value 214.463
Min value -1.12012

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2794
Mean 11.4924
Standard dev 2.27670
Max value 16.3910
Min value 3.55165

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 231.147

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2795
Mean 114.981
Standard dev 13.7256
Max value 139.382
Min value 91.8745

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 284.147

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

A579 20-SEP-97 P5 50' FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 142645-151323 Plotted 7-May-

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2793
Mean 634.628
Standard dev 195.591
Max value 1015.29
Min value 361.032

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2793
Mean 268.721
Standard dev 15.0766
Max value 292.792
Min value 240.409

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2793
Mean 253.355
Standard dev 20.2810
Max value 291.422
Min value 228.700

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2793
Mean 49.6542
Standard dev 12.4937
Max value 80.0247
Min value 29.2482

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2793
Mean 1.369276e-07
Standard dev 5.984715e-07
Max value 4.651471e-06
Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-J/S)

No of obs 2793
Mean 11.6887
Standard dev 1.01752
Max value 13.1808
Min value 8.53150

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2793
Mean 4069.33
Standard dev 2360.20
Max value 7902.69
Min value -16.9650

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2793
Mean 44.0773
Standard dev 2.526658e-02
Max value 44.1105
Min value 44.0132

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2793
Mean -27.7132
Standard dev 1.02732
Max value -26.0195
Min value -29.5506

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2793
Mean 11.1859
Standard dev 5.04662
Max value 19.3549
Min value 1.25158

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2793
Mean 13.9526
Standard dev 5.46495
Max value 22.3849
Min value 2.11194

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2793
Mean -0.758201
Standard dev 0.533150
Max value 0.386215
Min value -1.87614

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2793
Mean 17.9879
Standard dev 7.18090
Max value 29.0112
Min value 2.64457

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 231.280

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2793
Mean 116.277
Standard dev 13.6891
Max value 145.708
Min value 92.8148

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 270.542

A579 20-SEP-97 R4 FL260 From 151323-151822 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:34

A579 20-SEP-97 R4 FL260 From 151323-151822 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:34

A579 20-SEP-97 R4 FL260

From 151323-151822 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:34

A579 20-SEP-97 R4 FL260 From 151323-151822 Plotted 7-May-1998 10:34

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 298
 Mean 361.388
 Standard dev 0.552293
 Max value 362.654
 Min value 359.410

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 298
 Mean 240.736
 Standard dev 0.110157
 Max value 240.863
 Min value 240.332

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 298
 Mean 228.669
 Standard dev 0.611588
 Max value 230.572
 Min value 227.592

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 298
 Mean 57.7678
 Standard dev 3.74622
 Max value 69.8808
 Min value 53.7835

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 298
 Mean 1.000000e-38
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 1.000000e-38
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 298
 Mean 13.1113
 Standard dev 0.156675
 Max value 13.3790
 Min value 12.0695

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 298
 Mean 7895.87
 Standard dev 10.5997
 Max value 7933.89
 Min value 7871.61

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 298
 Mean 44.0048
 Standard dev 3.700909e-02
 Max value 44.0378
 Min value 43.9074

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 298
 Mean -29.7438
 Standard dev 0.104536
 Max value -29.5506
 Min value -29.8672

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 298
 Mean 16.2771
 Standard dev 0.821380
 Max value 19.5611
 Min value 14.9304

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 298
 Mean 22.5306
 Standard dev 0.760037
 Max value 24.1828
 Min value 21.3774

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 298
 Mean -0.956717
 Standard dev 0.245596
 Max value -0.381386
 Min value -1.67105

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 298
 Mean 27.8023
 Standard dev 0.925743
 Max value 30.8057
 Min value 26.4143

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 234.154

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 298
 Mean 140.566
 Standard dev 5.84369
 Max value 147.677
 Min value 125.717

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 237.803

A579 20-SEP-97 P6 FL260-50' R/FL200/FL150/FL130/FL110/FL50/500' From 151822-160509 Plotted

A579 20-SEP-97 P6 FL260-50' R/FL200/FL150/FL130/FL110/FL50/500' From 151822-160509 *Plotted*

A579 20-SEP-97 P6 FL260-50' R/FL200/FL150/FL130/FL110/FL50/500' From 151822-160509 Plotted

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 653.010
 Standard dev 184.493
 Max value 1016.20
 Min value 359.418

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 271.038
 Standard dev 13.7746
 Max value 293.996
 Min value 240.332

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 255.224
 Standard dev 19.8651
 Max value 291.622
 Min value 228.500

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 48.0959
 Standard dev 12.6117
 Max value 72.7358
 Min value 25.8007

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 2808
 Mean 8.250182e-07
 Standard dev 2.285202e-06
 Max value 2.589919e-05
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 10.8857
 Standard dev 1.92287
 Max value 13.1655
 Min value 5.52916

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 3802.27
 Standard dev 2173.82
 Max value 7933.73
 Min value -24.5220

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 42.6906
 Standard dev 0.669449
 Max value 43.9074
 Min value 41.5770

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 2808
 Mean -28.5679
 Standard dev 0.667134
 Max value -27.5322
 Min value -29.8432

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 11.9253
 Standard dev 4.28283
 Max value 19.4640
 Min value 1.95750

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 15.6858
 Standard dev 4.66389
 Max value 24.4780
 Min value 5.24509

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 0.148017
 Standard dev 0.573212
 Max value 1.79778
 Min value -1.34312

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 19.7765
 Standard dev 6.10235
 Max value 30.8907
 Min value 6.49511

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 232.756

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 2808
 Mean 116.119
 Standard dev 13.1913
 Max value 141.831
 Min value 91.8491

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 143.869

A579 20-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

A579 20-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

A579 20-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

A579 20--SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

A579 20-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

A579 20-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

A579 20-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

A579 20-SEP-97 P7 50'-FL260 R/100'/FL50/FL110/FL150/FL200 From 160509-165236 Plotted 7-May

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 2848
Mean 658.130
Standard dev 202.688
Max value 1015.72
Min value 360.359

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 2848
Mean 43.2341
Standard dev 8.88605
Max value 69.0754
Min value 29.9132

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 2848
Mean 3794.97
Standard dev 2404.99
Max value 7915.62
Min value -20.5414

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2848
Mean 7.47818
Standard dev 2.49155
Max value 11.4923
Min value 2.05241

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 2848
Mean 14.9228
Standard dev 3.60857
Max value 20.6049
Min value 5.49747

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 2848
Mean 272.522
Standard dev 14.1202
Max value 294.059
Min value 246.508

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()
No of obs 2848
Mean 8.008068e-07
Standard dev 2.508978e-06
Max value 1.919517e-05
Min value -1.046657e-09

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2848
Mean 40.4781
Standard dev 0.668862
Max value 41.5770
Min value 39.2795

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2848
Mean 12.7820
Standard dev 3.19446
Max value 18.2897
Min value 4.84004

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 2848
Mean 113.194
Standard dev 12.4918
Max value 148.351
Min value 90.4710

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 2848
Mean 266.603
Standard dev 16.9394
Max value 291.719
Min value 228.058

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)
No of obs 2848
Mean 11.1648
Standard dev 2.35217
Max value 17.5795
Min value 4.87372

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2848
Mean -26.4448
Standard dev 0.705411
Max value -25.1548
Min value -27.5322

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2848
Mean -0.689927
Standard dev 0.630951
Max value 0.854958
Min value -2.53098

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 141.647

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 239.670

A579 20-SEP-97 R5 FL260 From 165236-165639 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:08

A579 20-SEP-97 R5 FL260

From 165236 - 165639 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:08

A579 20-SEP-97 R5 FL260 From 165236-165639 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:08

A579 20-SEP-97 R5 FL260

From 165236-165639 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:08

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 244
 Mean 360.992
 Standard dev 0.410376
 Max value 361.932
 Min value 359.880

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 244
 Mean 246.611
 Standard dev 0.179165
 Max value 246.912
 Min value 246.227

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 244
 Mean 228.923
 Standard dev 1.57800
 Max value 232.500
 Min value 227.286

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 244
 Mean 59.1304
 Standard dev 1.11856
 Max value 61.8684
 Min value 57.0599

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 244
 Mean 1.000000e-38
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 1.000000e-38
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 244
 Mean 12.5998
 Standard dev 0.504924
 Max value 13.2120
 Min value 11.4854

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 244
 Mean 7903.46
 Standard dev 7.88037
 Max value 7924.83
 Min value 7885.42

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 244
 Mean 39.1609
 Standard dev 7.273820e-02
 Max value 39.2795
 Min value 39.0322

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 244
 Mean -25.0363
 Standard dev 6.929799e-02
 Max value -24.9183
 Min value -25.1548

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 244
 Mean 5.61539
 Standard dev 0.755844
 Max value 7.39513
 Min value 4.21619

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 244
 Mean 17.7968
 Standard dev 0.415608
 Max value 18.8904
 Min value 16.6370

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 244
 Mean -0.976495
 Standard dev 0.262763
 Max value -0.480423
 Min value -1.70301

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 244
 Mean 18.6785
 Standard dev 0.338484
 Max value 19.5153
 Min value 17.5369

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 252.488

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 244
 Mean 135.813
 Standard dev 7.19103
 Max value 144.427
 Min value 119.510

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 143.350

A579 20-SEP-97 P8 FL260-FL100 From 165639-170520 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:11

A579 20-SEP-97 P8 FL260-FL100 From 165639-170520 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:11

A579 20-SEP-97 P8 FL260-FL100 From 165639-170520 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:11

15 16 17 18 19 20

A579 20-SEP-97 R6 FL100 From 170520-171500 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:13

A579 20-SEP-97 R6 FL100

From 170520-171500 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:14

A579 20-SEP-97 R6 FL100 From 170520-171500 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:14

A579 20-SEP-97 R6 FL100

From 170520-171500 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:14

12 4

A579 20-SEP-97 R6 FL100

From 170520-171500 Plotted 7-May-1998 11:14

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 581
Mean 697.458
Standard dev 0.366933
Max value 698.695
Min value 696.764

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 581
Mean 278.453
Standard dev 0.356144
Max value 279.474
Min value 277.833

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 581
Mean 269.593
Standard dev 3.06032
Max value 276.392
Min value 260.422

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 581
Mean 43.9345
Standard dev 6.51212
Max value 56.0558
Min value 25.6864

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 581
Mean 1.337348e-06
Standard dev 2.444039e-06
Max value 1.157530e-05
Min value -1.046657e-09

JN02 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 581
Mean 9.16526
Standard dev 1.18809
Max value 10.7919
Min value 6.59312

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 581
Mean 3040.73
Standard dev 4.13169
Max value 3048.54
Min value 3026.80

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 581
Mean 38.1808
Standard dev 0.134692
Max value 38.4156
Min value 37.9409

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 581
Mean -24.1782
Standard dev 0.129634
Max value -24.0024
Min value -24.4003

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 581
Mean 5.36412
Standard dev 0.687313
Max value 6.75846
Min value 3.75096

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 581
Mean 11.0411
Standard dev 0.493669
Max value 12.1100
Min value 9.74683

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 581
Mean 9.564250e-02
Standard dev 0.724942
Max value 2.49545
Min value -0.892120

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 581
Mean 12.2878
Standard dev 0.636502
Max value 13.5915
Min value 10.6017

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 244.088

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 581
Mean 111.290
Standard dev 1.45975
Max value 114.865
Min value 107.186

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 147.792

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.

Particle Data

- **CNC:** Condensation nucleus counter (this data is provisional and requires further validation). The measurement is from a commercial instrument: TSI INC Model 3025A. Although CNC data were recorded on the flight no post flight processing has been carried out. Rather than delay this booklet further, I have decided to wait and process the data when the validation has been carried out by the cloud physics group.
- **PSAP:** The Radiance Research Particle Soot Absorption Photometer gives a measurement of optical absorption by black carbon, using a quartz filter with the absorption measured at 565 nm.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent and Ken Dewey (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (data not quality controlled). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data (approx) converted to ppb using approximate scale factor and offset. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_{xy}:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in bits. Only one NO_y channel was available for this flight. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section) to see when these were filled. Analysis carried out at NILU.
- **CO:** Approximate data in ppb from the DRS. Instrument scientist: Sandra Schmitgen (fz-Jülich).

Natural
Environment
Research
Council

ARASF

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